

GEORGE BERNARD SHAW AND HIS MASTERPIECE PYGMALION

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to George Bernard Shaw and his play Pygmalion. George Bernard Shaw is one of the most prolific writers in the West, and he even won a Nobel Prize. The play Pygmalion is a humanitarian comedy about love and the English class system. This play focuses on the idea that life is too realistic to believe in the fabrication of idealism.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola Jorj Bernard Shou va uning pyessasi Pigmalionga bag'ishlanadi. Jorj Bernard Shou G'arbdagi eng sermahsul yozuvchilardan biri va u hatto Nobel mukofotini ham qo'lga kiritgan. Pygmalion spektakli sevgi va ingliz sinf tizimi haqidagi gumanitar komediyadir. Bu asarda hayot idealizm uydirmasiga ishonib bo'lmaydigan darajada real, degan g'oyaga e'tibor qaratgan.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена Джорджу Бернару Шоу и его пьесе «Пигмалион». Джордж Бернад Шоу — один из самых плодовитых писателей на Западе, он даже получил Нобелевскую премию. Пьеса «Пигмалион» — гуманитарная комедия о любви и английской сословной системе. В этой работе он сосредоточился на идее о том, что жизнь слишком реальна, чтобы верить в вымысел идеализма.

Keywords: *George Bernard Shaw, Pygmalion, realism, society, playwright, drama, hero, dialect, plot, accent, prolific writer.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Jorj Bernard Shou, Pigmalion, realism, jamiyat, dramaturg, drama, qahramon, sheva, syujet, urg'u, sermahsul yozuvchi.*

Ключевые слова: *Джордж Бернад Шоу, Пигмалион, реализм, общество, драматург, драма, герой, диалект, сюжет, акцент, плодовитый писатель.*

Irish legend George Bernard Shaw was a playwright and literary critic, in addition to being a representative of socialism. He was awarded the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1925 for his valuable and outstanding contribution to literature, although he accepted the honor but declined the money. Another reason George Bernard Shaw is famous and respected is because he was a free thinker who advocated for women's rights and income equality. Shaw turned to literature and began his career by writing theater, criticism, music, and novels, one of which was the semi-autobiographical *Immaturity*. However, his initial efforts were neither recognized nor successful. From 1885 to 1911, Shaw served on the executive committee of the Fabian Society, a middle-class socialist group. The majority of Shaw's early plays examined current moral and social issues while emphasizing the drawbacks of

capitalism, *The Widower's Houses* is one of these dramas (1892). Sadly, these early initiatives did not meet with much success. Later works like *Candida* and *John Bull's Other Island* (1904) and *Major Barbara* turned out to be more to Shaw's liking. *Pygmalion*, his most well-known piece, was initially written for Mrs. Patrick Campbell. Later, *Pygmalion* was turned into two movies and a musical [1].

Pygmalion is a comedic play about the incredible transformation of a lower-class flower girl. *Pygmalion* has received a lot of attention since its publication, and although the play steadfastly rejected offers from filmmakers, Shaw, impressed by Gabriel Pascal's enthusiasm and talent, eventually agreed to film the play. In addition, the film released in 1938 was a significant success, after which the Irish playwright gained a large audience. *My Fair Lady* is a musical adaptation of Shaw's *Pygmalion*. *Pygmalion* is a comedic work. A comedy, in the theatrical sense, is a play that makes use of humor as a means of exploring the self and society. A comedy was a drama that had a happy ending to the Greeks. Despite the fact that no one dies in Shaw's comedy *Pygmalion*, questions about the characters' futures and whether Eliza will rejoin Higgins remain. The tension between Higgins and Eliza, which leads to a farce, serves as the drama's fundamental conflict, as does the question of whether she can now successfully maneuver through society given her new linguistic talents. The drama, which is subtitled "A Romance in Five Acts," cannot be defined as one in the conventional sense because the heroine, Eliza, and the hero, Higgins, do not get married. Despite being romantic and idealized, Eliza's metamorphosis from a flower girl on the streets to a lady would not be considered a classic romance. While some contend that the main romance is represented by Mr. Doolittle's common law marriage, others contend that it is represented by Eliza and Freddy's connection, despite the fact that it occurs primarily off-stage. The lesson Eliza learns about loving herself can be considered the true love story because Shaw is not a conventional author. She is independent and empowered to make her own decisions since she has grown to value herself [2].

I will write you an analysis of Act 1 and how it continues. The beginning of the play, which takes place on a rainy night, establishes the mood for the rest of the play. The audience develops understanding of the various socioeconomic classes' conduct. The Eynsford Hills, a wealthy family consisting of a mother, daughter, and son, are shown calling a taxi to get away from the storm as the lower classes endure it. Shaw distinguishes the classes based on their actions, demeanor, speech, and dialect. The audience observes how important characteristics of a person's behavior, appearance, and communication determine their social class. The main plot is around a young girl with a strong accent trying to sell flowers to an elderly man. A man who is taking notes or observing people can determine the social origins and lifestyles of those he observes.

Act II. Eliza Dolittle, the flower girl, arrives at Professor Higgins' home the following morning. She asks him to teach her how to talk after hearing him say that he could turn a

flower girl into a duchess. Eliza wants to improve her speech so she can sell flowers in a store rather than on the street. While his colleague Pickering treats Eliza with kindness and respect, Higgins makes fun of her despite the fact that she is powerless to defend herself vocally. Pickering offers to cover Eliza's tuition costs in exchange for Higgins teaching her how to behave like a duchess at the Ambassador's party because he wants to help Eliza. Eliza will attend lessons while residing with Higgins for six months. The housekeeper, Mrs. Pearce, leads Eliza upstairs to take a bath. Her father, Mr. Alfred Dolittle, shows up as she is taking a bath and appears upset that his daughter is missing. He truly only wants money because he is drunk. Eliza returns to the room with Mrs. Pearce, clean. Even her father is unable to identify her as he exits the house, indicating that her change has already started.

Act III is the first of several tests of Eliza and her transformation from flower girl to lady. She is the guest of Professor Higgins' mother, Mrs. Higgins. She is introduced to her wealthy family, the Emsford Hills, from the beginning of the play. Her son Freddie Emsford Hill, a humble aristocrat and bachelor, listens intently to her story. When Higgins and Pickering first meet her on the street selling flowers, her excitement causes Eliza's speech to revert to her Cockney accent. This dialect is indicative of the working class and creates a disconnect in communication between social classes. Although her pronunciation and appearance have improved, Eliza has certain qualities that betray her origin: she talks about her father's alcoholism, her aunt's flu, walks without taking a taxi She's mad at me for asking me to. A Mrs. who acts as the voice of reason in the play. Higgins is angry with the men who undertook this experiment, and warns that there will be consequences once the game is over. I commented that it can't be hidden.

The process of reading the analysis of this comedic play was very meaningful and mysterious for me. Moreover, this comedy shows of Shaw taught me to achieve my goal no matter what. While the film and musical have garnered a lot of attention, the show's original play is more insightful and conveys a far-reaching, down-to-earth meaning. Shaw is by no means a sentimental playwright. The focus on the Pygmalion myth shows the author's strong desire for social reform. As such, Shaw is a prominent member of the Fabian Society of Great Britain, which promotes social reform. With its realistic ending, the show does not intend to evoke strong emotions in its audience with Pygmalion, but it does so in a didactic way to make them think that in this economic society, business has the highest say in social life. I plan to but he is against moral decay. They use drama to portray social realities, disseminate social ideas, and inspire audiences to bring those ideas to life.

REFERENCES:

1. Shaw, Bernard, *Pygmalion: a Romance in Five Acts*, Longman Group Ltd., 1981, pp. 103.
2. Shaw G.B. *Pygmalion*. New York: Pocket Books, Simon & Schuster, Inc., 2005.

INTERNET RESOURCES:

1. <https://www.studysmarter.co.uk/explanations/english-literature/american-drama/pygmalion-overview/>
2. <https://www.famousauthors.org/george-bernard-sha>